

Table 2. Frequency distribution of races of *X. campestris* in different regions of the Philippines, 1980-82, IRRI.

Region	Year	Isolates (no.)						Total
		Race 1	Race 2	Race 3	Race 4	Race 5	Race 6	
Ilocos region	1981	0	6	0	0	0	0	6
Mt. Province	1981	0	0	0	0	2	0	2
	1982	0	0	0	0	2	0	2
Nueva Ecija	1980	0	31	0	0	0	0	31
	1981	0	2	0	0	0	0	2
	1982	0	1	0	0	0	0	1
Central Luzon (other than Nueva Ecija)	1981	0	7	0	0	0	0	7
Laguna and Quezon	1980	1	2	0	0	0	4	7
	1981	0	1	0	1	0	0	2
	1982	1	41	0	1	0	2	45
Bicol region	1980	0	0	5	0	0	0	5
	1981	0	2	0	0	0	0	2
	1982	0	4	10	0	0	0	14
Visayas region	1980	0	1	0	0	0	0	1
	1981	0	5	0	0	0	0	5
	1982	0	4	1	0	0	0	5
Davao	1980	0	7	3	0	0	0	10
	1981	0	5	1	0	0	0	6
	1982	0	43	1	0	0	0	44
Cotabato	1982	0	7	0	0	0	0	7
Mindanao (other than Davao and Cotabato)	1982	0	5	0	0	0	0	5
Total		2	174	21	2	4	6	209
Percent		0.95	83.3	10.0	0.95	1.9	2.9	

undescribed races 5 and 6 were also identified. In 1980-82, an average of 80% of the rice growing areas in the Philippines was planted to modern varieties, including IR varieties.

We grouped the populations by collection site. Race 2 was found everywhere but in Mountain Province (Table 2). Only Laguna (including IRRI) showed races virulent not only to IR20 but also to IR1545-339, with *xa 5* gene, and moderately virulent to DV85, with *xa 5* and *Xa 7* genes, infrequently: 3.7% for IR1545-339 and 2.9% for DV85. The previously dominant race 1 had markedly decreased frequency. In Bicol, particularly in Camarines Sur, race 3 dominated. In Davao, race 2 had overtaken the previously dominant race 3. □

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Variability of field population of the bacterial blight (BB) pathogen of rice

C. M. Vera Cruz and T. W. Mew, Plant Pathology Department, IRRI

Previous studies have shown that length of lesions induced by isolates of the rice BB pathogen varied in individual varieties. We sought to determine the extent of variability of the BB pathogen in a population by studying the virulence of an isolate as expressed in lesion variance caused by the isolate on a variety.

The isolates were inoculated on IR8 and IR1545-339 40 d after sowing by clipping the 2 youngest fully expanded leaves of each active tiller. Lesions of each isolate on each variety were measured on 20 leaves 14 d after inoculation and evaluated for variance.

Scatter-diagrams of lesion variance on IR8, IR20, and IR1545 are shown in Figures 1, 2, and 3. Lesion variance was high on IR8, which is susceptible to all isolates, and on IR20, which is susceptible

1. Variation in virulence of the field population of *X. c. pv. oryzae*, 1980-82, expressed as variance of lesions induced on IR8, IRRI.

to races 2, 3, 6, and variable to race 4. On IR1545, which is resistant to all but races

4 and 6, lesion variance was lower than on IR8 and IR20, but increased propor-

2. Variation in virulence of the field population of *X. c. pv. oryzae*, 1980-82, expressed as variance of lesions induced on IR20, IRRI.

3. Variation in virulence of the field population of *X. c. pv. oryzae*, 1980-82, expressed as variance of lesions induced on IR1545, IRRI. One extreme value (20.76 cm²) in 1982 was not plotted.

tionally with mean lesion length induced by races 4 and 6. This may indicate the inherent variability of the BB pathogen as affected by the nature of resistance of

the variety.

The *Xa 4* gene for resistance of IR20 was overcome by the predominant pathogen race. □

Ufra incidence in summer rice in West Bengal

H. S. Chakrabarti, D. K. Nayak, and A. Pal, Rice Research Station, Chinsurah, Hooghly, West Bengal, India

Ufra disease, caused by the nematode *Ditylenchus augustus* (Butler) Filipjev, usually affects the winter rice crop. But in 1984, it was recorded in the summer crop on a Ganges River island in Hooghly, West Bengal. The crop was flooded because of a high tide for 5-6 d in mid-Mar. There was a marked increase in disease 1 wk after partial submergence, when the crop was at tillering-to-stem extension.

Symptoms were leaf yellowing, especially of young leaves; twisted bases of young leaves; distorted leaf sheaths (Fig. a); and swollen lower nodes with irregular nodal branching (Fig. b). At later growth, panicles wrinkled and emerged only partially. Sometimes they did not emerge. Spikelets were partially

Infected plant parts with ufra symptoms: a. twisted base of a younger leaf; b. swollen node with nodal branching, wrinkling, and panicle distortion; and c. sterile spikelets, West Bengal, India.